

Waste Paper Recycling: Contributions to Giresun and Turkey Economies

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Abstract

Paper recycling is the process of turning waste paper into new paper products such as newspaper, corrugated boxes, tissue products and egg boxes etc. With population growth and technological developments, paper consumption rate is increasing rapidly. For this reason, recovery rate of waste paper, which is cheaper than wood cellulose and important in terms of environment, is also rapidly increasing. Due to the high amount of chemicals and water used in chemical methods and the awareness of consumers about the environment, the demand on waste paper has increased.

Approximately 15-20% of the garbage collected by the municipalities consists of paper. Waste paper recycling rate in Turkey is about 55% and this rates varies between 70-75% in Europe. Therefore, the collections of waste papers and re-evaluation in the paper sector have become an inevitable industrial activity today.

The aim of this study has to investigate contribution of Giresun province and Turkey to economies in terms of waste paper collecting and recycling.

Keywords: Giresun, waste paper, recycling, economy

1. Introduction

Paper production and consumption in Turkey has increased rapidly in the last ten years. Depending on population growth, technological development, industrialization and urbanization in our country, waste paper usage in paper production is also increasing every year. Recycling of used paper makes an important contribution both to protect the environment and to increase the variety of raw material usage.

The use of wood in the paper industry is decreasing day by day due to the inadequacy of raw materials in our country. The use of waste paper as an alternative raw material to wood in the paper industry has contributed to solving the problem of raw materials. Approximately 15% of waste paper is contained in the garbage collected by the municipalities. By using waste paper in the paper industry, large and small-sized factories can be established and at the same time, it has lots of advantages such as low raw material, energy, water usage, easy control of production technique and equipment (Tutus, 2004).

Efforts are being made to support the raw material resources of the paper industry, such as the use of fast-growing tree species, annual crops and waste paper in paper production, as well as reducing the pressure on the forests. The quantities of wood, annual plant and waste paper used in the paper industry in the world and our country in 2015 were given below in Figures 1 and 2, respectively (FAOSTAT, 2016).

Figure 1. Raw materials and ratios used in the paper industry in the world in 2015

Figure 2. Raw materials and ratios used in the paper industry in Turkey in 2015

Solid wastes have a heterogeneous structure and the composition is constantly changing. The amount and quality of solid wastes produced by each country are very different from each other. This is because the socio-economic and financial structures as well as consumption habits and similar characteristics are very different from each other. In developed countries, the production of solid waste is 1.5-2 kg / person-day. While this value reaches to 3.0 kg / person-day in America, the average daily amount of solid waste per person in our country is 1.14 kg for summer season, 1.09 kg for winter season and 1.12 kg for a year. The average amount of waste per person in Giresun province is 1,12 kg /person-day for 2016 (EUROSTAT, 2014; TUIK, 2017).

In this study, the raw materials and ratios used in paper production in our country, the amount of paper and cardboard produced and consumed the collection and evaluation of waste papers and contributions to the economy of Giresun and Turkey were investigated.

2. Quantity of Paper-Cardboard Produced and Consumed in Our Country and Recycling Rates

There are currently 49 factories producing paper and cardboard in our country. World paper-cardboard production is 764 million tons. Our country is ranked 42nd with 78.3 kg/person paper-cardboard consumption, 14th with 6.326.345 tons paper-cardboard consumption, and 23rd with 4.356.823 tons paper-cardboard production in the world (FAOSTAT, 2016; SKSV, 2017).

Ranked 14th and 23rd with paper-cardboard consumption and production in the world reveals that our country mostly imports papers. This figure reflects the truth is that Turkey is a country open to the growth of the paper and cardboard industry.

Paper-cardboard and pulp production and consumption in our country, per person paper consumption and recycling rates were given separately in Tables 1, 2, 3, and 4 below (SKSV, 2017).

Table 1. Paper and cardboard production quantities in Turkey

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Newsprint	836	0	0	0	0
Writing-printing papers	257.000	262.650	232.500	237.100	247.000
Wrapping papers	83.081	96.303	80.000	75.000	77.750
Corrugated papers	1.609.215	1.842.447	2.190.028	2.280.352	2.514.534
Cartons	568.407	459.550	577.291	614.989	643.342
Tissue papers	568.861	584.827	660.487	811.572	869.197
Special papers	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000
Total	3.092.400	3.250.777	3.745.306	4.024.013	4.356.823

Table 2. Paper and cardboard consumption quantities in Turkey

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Newsprint	435.191	390.636	346.353	261.814	224.145
Writing-printing papers	1.204.143	1.206.573	1.177.169	1.202.181	1.203.430
Wrapping papers	334.195	351.404	329.139	288.791	344.859
Corrugated papers	2.261.136	2.394.251	2.468.107	2.608.233	2.786.315
Cartons	1.000.810	1.003.515	1.026.093	1.078.303	1.180.065
Tissue papers	402.222	438.268	494.484	539.566	560.588
Special papers	19.824	21.358	23.634	25.031	26.943
Total	5.657.521	5.806.005	5.864.979	6.003.919	6.326.345

Paper consumption and recycling rates, which are accepted as indicators of economic development all over the world, have increased in our country depending on years, as seen in Table 3 and Table 4 below.

Table 3. Paper and paperboard consumption amounts per person in Turkey (kg)

2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
68.6	69.2	70.7	73.8	74.7	74.5	75.2	78.3

Table 4. Waste paper recycling rate in Turkey (%)

2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
41.8	44.4	45.1	44.8	46.4	49.2	52.2	54.0

First of all, it should be essential to realize the use of the things in the most effective and most functional manner. This may be possible with effective consumer awareness. In other words, contrary to the "use/throw" philosophy, it is necessary to try not to produce waste and garbage as much as possible. In this regard, especially in Canada, good work and public awareness programs are being carried out. In the 4 R method; 1-Reduce: Reduce the amount of garbage and waste if possible. 2-Reuse: To use the material again and again if possible. 3-Recycling: To use the most effective material in recycling process. 4-Recovery: To feed and enrich raw materials (Miner et al., 1993).

In our country and in the province of Giresun, the main sources of waste papers are collected at low cost;

- All kind of paper, cardboard and corrugated cardboard supplied from industrial establishments and major shopping centers,
- Old newspapers, cardboard boxes and magazines collected from home and work places,
- Different types of papers collected from educational institutions,
- Clippings from press, envelopes and notebook producers
- Corrugated cardboards, bag and bag making workshop residues.

3. Contributions of Waste Paper Recycling to Giresun and Country Economies

We can collect the contribution of the waste paper collection to the province and country economies under 4 headings.

1. Contribution to the Protection of the Environment
2. Contribution to the Protection of Forests
3. Contribution to Municipality
4. Contribution to Paper Production

3.1. Contribution to the Protection of the Environment

A well-organized collection system will not only relieve municipal solid waste collection loads, but will also prevent disposal in garbage dumps. In addition, the use of less wood, water, electricity and chemicals required for manufacturing is very important in terms of environmental protection if production is made using waste paper.

Improving environmental awareness in the collection of waste paper reduces the cost of transporting and disposing of solid wastes, and it is important for the health of people working in garbage dumps prior to the disposal process.

In a study carried out by Giresun Provincial Directorate of Environment and Forestry, province recyclable additive composition ratio (paper, glass, metal and plastic) was determined as 25%, of which 5% is waste paper (KCRD, 2016). If waste papers is collected in Giresun by separating it from its source, it will pour approximately 7.5 tons less garbage in one day, 225 tons less garbage in a month, 2700 tons (1080 trucks) less garbage in year.

3.2. Contribution to the Protection of Forests

In 2017, our per person annual paper consumption is 78.3 kg (SKSV, 2017).

$134,937$ (Provincial population) \times 78.3 kg = 10 thousand 566 tons of annual paper consumption

1 ton paper is produced from 17 adult trees.

10.566×17 trees (1 ton of pulp) = 179.622 adult trees will be cut less.

1 ton of paper is produced from 2.5 m^3 ($10.566 \times 2.5 \text{ m}^3 = 26.415 \text{ m}^3$).

$26.415 \text{ m}^3 \times 150 \text{ TL} / \text{m}^3$ (the price of wood for 1 ton of paper) = 3 million 962 thousand 250 TL.

If the total amount of paper-cardboard per person (1,727 tons) in Giresun can be collected, 3 million 962 thousand 250 TL will be contributed to the protection of forests. The recycling rate in our country is 54% and will contribute at least 2 million 140 thousand TL to the provincial economy.

In Table 5 below, the amounts of wood, water and electrical energy required to produce 1 ton of paper from wood and waste paper are given. According to this table, 110% more wood raw material, about 13 times more water and 1.5 times more electricity will be harmed around the environment to produce first quality paper instead of waste paper (CEKUL, 2002).

Table 5. Quantities of wood, water and electricity required to produce 1 ton of paper from wood and waste paper

1 TON PAPER			
PAPER TYPE	WOOD	WATER	ENERGY
I. Quality Paper	2400 Kg	100 tons	7.600 kwh
II. Quality Paper	1700 Kg	80 tons	5.700 kwh
Eco-Friendly Recycled Paper	1150 Kg Waste Paper	8 tons	4.800 kwh

3.3. Contribution to Municipality

The average amount of garbage collected by the municipality in the province center (151 tons per day) is 4,534 tons/month. Approximately 5% of the garbage collected is waste paper (KCRD, 2016).

$4.534 \times 0.05 = 227$ tons waste paper.

227×400 TL (1 ton waste paper sale price) = 90 thousand 800 TL.

If a regular collection network is developed on a provincial basis;

$90,800 \times 12$ (1 year) = 1 million 89 thousand 600 TL / year will stay in the municipality.

3.4. Contribution to Paper Production

In 2017, our per person annual paper consumption is 78.3 kg (SKSV, 2017).

$134,937$ (Provincial population) $\times 78.3$ kg = 10 thousand 566 tons of annual paper consumption

If half of this amount can be collected;

$10566/2 = 5$ thousand 283 tons of paper is collected.

1 ton of new paper is produced from approximately 1,150 kg waste paper. Approximately 4 thousand 594 tons of paper are produced from 5 thousand 283 tons waste paper.

4594×1100 TL (1 ton price) = 5 million 53 thousand 400 TL

If 50% of the papers collected after the use is collected, the total contribution to Giresun Economy in 1 year will be approximately 2 million 526 thousand 700 TL.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

The paper and paperboard to be recovered by establishing a more effective waste collection network in Giresun and its provinces will provide the following contributions to the provincial economy and consequently to the country's economy.

1. Approximately 2.724 tons of waste paper will be thrown away in a year in the center of Giresun, where it will be recovered from being destroyed or destroyed and turned into paper again.
2. By collecting waste papers, the problem of environmental pollution will be reduced. In addition, contamination of the waste residues by the surrounding environment and the cost of cleaning it will be reduced.

3. Forest resources will be better protected and each ton of recycled waste paper will save 17 adult trees from cutting. Adult 1 tree meets the daily oxygen requirement of 52 people.

To collect effective and efficient waste paper in our country and in our province; inform people, to keep the level of consciousness continuously with the written and visual press, to distribute office-based paper collection bags, to place waste paper collection boxes in corridor, floors and buildings, to determine a place where collected papers are collected and piled up, to put spot and flat panel suggesting ads and words about the importance of recovering at certain locations in the city. Along with these, it has become a necessity for local managers to initiate legal sanctions such as rewarding and punishing for effective recycling.

Since the practitioner will be a human being by reviving this, it is extremely important for people to be conscious of starting from the young age. A conscious and responsible consumer who knows the value of waste paper for the environment, nature, forest and economy will reach the nearest waste paper collection box and recycle even the smallest piece of paper when necessary.

As a result, collection of waste papers, which will contribute significantly to the province and hence the country's economy, should be actively supported by municipalities, public and non-governmental organizations.

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